

Quality Assurance in Office Technology and Management Programmes in Polytechnics Education: A Panacea for Skill Acquisition and Self Reliance in South-South Nigeria.

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Abstract

The study investigated quality assurance in Office Technology and Management program (OTM) in Polytechnics in South- South, Nigeria. Descriptive survey research was used for the study. Two purposes of study, two research questions and corresponding two null hypotheses guided the study. The population of the study consisted of one hundred and sixteen (116) lecturers; there was no sample as the entire population was investigated. Eighty six (86) copies of questionnaires were retrieved from the one hundred and sixteen copies distributed, (38 males and 49 females). Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions and t-test statistics was used to test the two null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The results showed that respondents are in agreement with the items listed for the study as the grand mean for research questions 1 and 2 were rated 3.04 and 3.63 respectively, which is above 2.50, which was the boundary limit set for the study. The hypotheses tested revealed that there was no significant difference in the opinions of experienced and less experienced lecturers, on the causes of poor quality assurance mechanism and also there was no significant difference in the opinions of male and female lecturers on how to improve quality assurance programme. It was recommended among others that regulatory agencies such as NBTE saddled with supervision, accreditation and reaccreditation of polytechnics should visit institutions offering OTM programmes yearly to ascertain compliance and that qualified lecturers, instructors and technologies should be engaged to ensure academic excellence.

Key words: Education, Quality, assurance, Skill, Acquisition, Office, Technology, Management.

Introduction

Education is today a key factor in the development of human and material resources in every nation. It is a process for transmission, preservation and improvement of the culture of a people. According to Offorma (2016), education is a process through which human beings become morally good members of their society. Education is relied upon as the bedrock and tool for nation building. This implies that no meaningful development can take place in a country that

lacks adequately trained manpower no matter how well endowed such a nation might be. This was rightly affirmed by Adegbesan in Garba, Jah and Dahiru (2017) that people and nations are what they are because of the nature and types of education they have been exposed to. It is in recognition of developing society that governments of many nations commit immense resources to the educational sector to ensure citizens are trained to acquire the desired skills; also policies are tailored towards ensuring accessibility to the general public.

Quality assurance according to Nwada and Seyi (2017) is a general philosophy pervading all aspects of a systems activity. It is the establishment of standard in various processes and activities that lead to the attainment of quality result. Onyesom and Ashibogwu (2013) viewed quality assurance in education as performance measures designed by authorities for assessing the performance of institutions with a view to ensuring that learning outcomes meet needs of each society. It is the systematic management and assessment procedures adopted by higher education institutions and systems to monitor performance against objectives and to ensure achievement of quality outputs and improvement.

Maduwesi and Onyeachi (2010) stated that the heart of education is quality. Similarly Ogunribido in Oluwadare (2019) observed that the central issue in the production of any product be it material or human is quality. Therefore quality assurance mechanism in office technology and management education programme could not be over emphasised as it is the only panacea to producing quality graduates that can be accommodated in the present technological environment. It is the gateway to achieving the needed skills and it is the recipe to inculcate creativity and innovation among graduates in order to be self sufficient.

Office Technology and Management programme (OTM) is an educational programme offered under the Business Education programme in Nigeria Universities and Colleges of Education, as well as a programme of study in the Polytechnics in Nigeria. It is a comprehensive activity based educational programme that is concerned with the acquisition of office vocational skills, understanding, attitudes, works habits and competencies that are requisite to success in office management occupations. It is an efficient, effective, productive and functional education which leads itself to self employment, self reliance, paid-employment and consequently self actualisation. According to the National Board for Technical Education (NBTE) (2008), the objectives of OTM programme in the Polytechnics include equipping the students with knowledge, competencies and specific skills that enable them to successfully hold positions as secretaries, managers in public and private sectors of the economy and to be self employed. The programme exposes students to industrial work experience to practice their skills and equally develop students' potentials for further academic and Professional pursuit and to acquire occupational intelligence that will make them versatile and adaptable to changing situations in the world of works. In order to achieve the stated objectives, students of the programme are exposed to courses in education and in their special areas which include foundation courses, professional courses, entrepreneurship development and supervised industrial work experience scheme (SIWES). The training is to enable recipients to acquire vocational and interpersonal skills for effective work competencies.

In every trade, if skills are lacking, it is a justification that the right training is not given. Skill is the ability to do something well (Oluwadare 2019). Skill usually is the art of possessing the ability to power, authority or competency to do the task required of an individual on the job. It has to do with expert knowledge and creative reasoning to a level of mastery (Sokyes, Wetnwan and Bewaran 2018). Skills acquisition on the other hand, is the ability to be trained on a particular task or function and becomes expert in it. (Anyeadu 2020). Skills acquisition can do a lot of great work in the life of every person. Oluwadare (2019) noted that skills acquisition is the recipe for eradicating extreme poverty and hunger by creating an avenue for employment, thereby creating an avenue for jobs and wealth creation while instilling self- sufficiency and reliance. Skill acquisition is the key in the fight for the elimination of joblessness and reduction of crime through effective engagement. Acquiring skills in OTM help recipients to engage on productive work either for themselves or for employers of labour. This enables the students to qualify for paid jobs as well as increase their productivity and earn more remuneration.

However, the situation on ground shows that OTM graduates have joined the labour market queue. Also they are not able to run their own businesses and those who venture into businesses have not been successful. This is an indication that OTM programmes have lost focus of the primary aim of the programme which is, to prepare individuals to be entrepreneurially and skillfully functional in the society. In support of this view, Okoli, Utoware and Kaizer (2018) stress that most graduates of Business Education which include OTM graduates in Nigeria are without gainful employment and the products of the programme are ill equipped and short of the necessary skills for self realisation and national development. This means the programme quality has declined and as such acquisition of the required skill is no longer attained. This no doubt has affected graduates of the programme in the area of job placement.

Statement of the Problem

The main objective of Polytechnic education in Nigeria is the promotion of technical and vocational education and training, technology transfer as well as skills development. This is in line with the aim of Nigeria education system at the tertiary level which include, contributing to national development through high level manpower training, to acquire both physical and intellectual skills which will enable individuals to be self-reliant and useful members of the society (NPE 2000). The graduates of OTM programme from the Polytechnics should acquire maximum skills for self development and to gain job placement in the labour market.

Regrettably, due to poor mechanism in regulating education system in Nigeria, quality assurance in education is absent and this has affected graduates of OTM programmes negatively, as many graduates are without jobs and the relevant skills to practice are lacking. Against this background, this study is carried out to explore quality assurance mechanism that could be put in place in order to achieve the programme objectives.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study is to explore quality assurance mechanism that could improve the training of students of office technology and management programme. The study sought to:

1. Determine causes of poor quality assurance mechanism adopted in office technology and management programme in South-South Nigeria.
2. Determine quality assurance mechanism to improve office technology and management programmes in South-South, Nigeria.

Research Questions

Two research questions guided the study; they are;

1. What are the causes of poor quality assurance mechanism adopted in office technology and management programmes in South-South, Nigeria?
2. What are the quality assurance mechanisms to improve office technology and management programmes in South-South, Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The following two null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant difference in the mean rating of more experienced and less experienced lecturers in Office Technology and Management programmes in South - South, Nigeria.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean rating of male and female lecturers in office technology and management programmes in South – South, Nigeria.

METHOD

The study adopted descriptive research survey design. This enables the researcher to sample the opinion of the target population which comprises lecturers from Office Technology and Management programmes in Polytechnics in South–South, Nigeria. The population of the study consisted of 116 lecturers. There was no sampling because the population for the study was not too large. .

The study employed a self structured questionnaire which contain 29 items on a 4 point scale of strongly Agree = 4 point, Agree =3 point, Disagree = 2 point and strongly disagree = 1 point. The instrument was validated by three experts, their comments and suggestions were incorporated in the questionnaire to enrich the instrument.

The decision rule for the study was established at a mean of 2.50 and above while any mean less than that was not accepted. Cronbach Alpha reliability method was used to establish the internal

consistency of the instrument which yielded coefficient index of 0.80 and 0.83 respectively which suggested that the instrument was reliable. The researcher administered 116 copies of the questionnaire with the help of 3 research assistants in the 11 public Polytechnics in South-South Nigeria. Eighty six (86) copies of the questionnaires were retrieved and used for the study. This gives 74% return rate. The data collected were analysed using descriptive statistics of mean to answer the research questions and standard deviation to determine the homogeneity or otherwise of the respondents' views, while t-test statistics was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance, using statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) version 21.

Results

Research question 1

What are the causes of poor quality assurance mechanism adopted in OTM programme in South – South, Nigeria?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation on the causes of poor quality assurance mechanism adopted in OTM programmes.

S/N	Items	Mean	S D	Decision
1.	Non compliance with Curriculum Implementation	2.48	0.52	Disagree
2.	Near absence of training Equipment and machines	3.15	0.94	Agree
3.	Inability to maintain available Equipment and machines	3.49	0.87	Agree
4.	Poor founding of OTM programmes	3.68	1.01	Strongly Agree
5.	Near absence of Laboratories for training student.	3.29	0.68	Agree
6.	Minimum standard set by NBTE are not adhered to	3.65	0.65	Agree
7.	Number of admitted students is higher than approval streams	3.72	0.95	Strongly Agree
8.	Students are not exposed to equipment and machines they will meet in real work situation	3.00	0.75	Agree

9. Improper monitoring of OTM programmes by NBTE	3.25	1.07	Agree
10. Curriculum use is no longer in tune with current reality.	2.51	1.04	Agree
11. Most Lecturers in the programme are out of touch with what the labour market demands	2.51	0.96	Agree
13. Corrupt practices, by leaders rendered OTM programmes ineffective.	2.62	1.01	Agree
Grand mean/standard deviation	2.62	1.01	Agree

The data in table 1 show that respondents' rated two (2) items as strongly agree. They include items 4 and 7 with mean scores of 3.68 and 3.72, ten (10) items were rated agreed, they are items 2, 3,5,6,8,9,10,11,12 and 13, with mean scores of 3.15, 3.49,3.29,3.65,3.00,3.25,2.51,2.51, 2.86 and 2.62 respectively. Only item one was rated disagree. However with a grand mean of 3.09, it is an indication that lecturers rated items listed in table one, as causes of poor quality assurance mechanism adopted in OTM programme. The standard deviation which is within 0.52- 1.07 shows that the respondents were homogenous in their responses.

Research question 2: What are the quality assurance mechanisms to improve OTM programmes in South-South, Nigeria?

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation of quality assurance mechanisms to improve OTM programmes in South-South, Nigeria.

S/N	Items	Mean	S D	Decision
14.	Redesigning the OTM curriculum By NBTE to inject new areas of ICT in the programme.	3.91	1.30	strongly agree
15.	Supervision by NBTE should be done with renewed vigour.	3.82	1.05	strongly agree
16.	NBTE should ensure that reaccreditation is done every 3 years as against the 5 years at present.	2.76	0.91	Agree

17. Any Polytechnic found to admit above the stream allotted should be sanctioned.	3.58	0.83	Strongly agree
18. Adequate Laboratory equipments should be provided	3.92	0.96	Strongly agree
19. Lecture's rooms and Laboratory should befit the modern times.	3.82	1.02	strongly agree
20. Students should be supervised/evaluated properly.	3.61	0.79	strongly agree
21. There should be increase in lecturers contacts with students.	2.71	1.08	Agree
22. There should be quality selection guidelines to aid admission of students.	3.32	0.76	Agree
23. Available infrastructure and facilities should be maintained promptly.	3.90	0.81	strongly agree
24. There should be good governance devoid of corrupt practices.	3..96	0.92	Strongly agree
25. Students industrial work experience scheme should be redesigned to ensure its impact on students.	3.62	0.98	strongly agree
26. Students that play truancy in the SIWES should be made to face disciplinary actions.	3.71	1.02	strongly agree
27. There should be collaboration between industries and Polytechnics especially OTM programmes to aid training of students in the practical areas.	3.86	0.76	strongly agree
28. Impact assessment should be carried out every 5 years by owners of Public polytechnics to ascertain the level of growth in the system	3.76	1.02	Strongly agree

29. Qualified lecturers should be employed	3.63	0.93	Strongly agree
Grand mean /standard deviation	3.61	0.93	strongly agree

The data in table 2 show that respondents rated items 16, 21, and 22 as agreed with mean scores of 2.76, 2.71 and 3.32. Thirteen (13) items were rated strongly agreed, they are items 14,15,17,18,19,20,23,24,25,26,27,28, and 29 with mean scores of 3.91, 3.82,3.58,3.92, 3.82,3.61,3.90,3.62,3.71,3.86,3.76, and 3.63 respectively. None of the items listed was rated disagreed or strongly disagreed. With a grand mean of 3.61, which fall within the value of strongly agree, it is an indication that lecturers are in agreement that, all the items listed are quality assurance mechanism to improve OTM programmes for skill acquisition and self reliance in South-South, Nigeria. The standard deviation which ranges from 0.72-1.30 shows that respondents were not far apart in their opinions.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in the mean rating of more experienced and less experienced lecturers on causes of poor quality assurance adopted in OTM programmes in South-South, Nigeria.

Table 3: Summary of t-test analysis of experienced and less experienced lecturers on causes of poor quality assurance mechanism adopted in South-South Nigeria.

S/N	Sources of Variance	N	X	SD	DF	P	t-cal.	t-crit.	Decision
1.	Experienced Lecturers	38	3.12	0.67	83	0.05	0.68	1.96	Acceptance
2.	Less experienced Lecturers	47	3.24	0.61					

Key: N = No of Respondent X = mean, S D = standard deviation, Df = Degree of freedom, P = level of significance, t-cal = t-calculated, t-crit = t-critical (table)

Result on table 3 indicates that t-calculated value of 0.68 is less than the tabulated value of 1.96 at 0.05 levels of significance and 83 degree of freedom. This implies that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of experienced and less experienced lecturers, hence the hypothesis was accepted.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference in the mean rating of male and female lecturers on quality assurance mechanism to improve OTM programmes in South-South, Nigeria

Table 4: Summary of t-test analysis of quality assurance mechanism to improve OTM programme.

S/N	Sources of Variance	N	X	SD	DF	P	t-cal.	t-crit.	Decision
1.	Male	38	3.12	0.67	83	0.05	0.68	1.96	Acceptance
2.	Female	49	3.14	0.75					

Key: N = No of Respondent X = mean, S D = standard deviation, Df = Degree of freedom, P = level of significance, t-cal = t-calculated, t-crit = t-critical (table)

Result on table 4 shows that the t-calculated value of 0.56 is less than the tabulated value of 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance and 83 degree of freedom. This indicates that there is no significant difference in the opinion of male and female lecturers on quality assurance mechanism to improve OTM programme in South-South, Nigeria. Therefore the hypothesis was accepted.

Discussion

The findings of research question one revealed that respondents are in agreement with all the items listed as causes of poor quality assurance mechanism in OTM programme. They include near absence of training equipment and machines, inability to maintain available equipment, poor funding, non compliance to NBTE minimum standard, non exposure of students to equipment and machines they will meet in work situation, present curriculum not in tune with current reality, lecturers in the programme are out of touch with labour market demands, poor management and corrupt practices. The findings of research question one is in agreement with the views of Dahel and Diyoshake (2017) who concluded that quality output from the nation’s colleges of education in particular and other institutions of learning in the country has definitely dwindled over the years due to neglect of the sector for the past decades.

The result of findings from research questions two (2) equally indicates that respondents agreed to items listed as quality assurance mechanisms to improve OTM programmes. They include; redesigning the OTM curriculum by NBTE to inject new areas of ICT, supervision of institutions should be done with vigour, accreditations should be done every 3 years, admission of students should be within the streams allotted, adequate laboratory equipment should be provided, increase in lecturers contact hours with students, adherence to selection guidelines, maintenance of available infrastructure and facilities, good governance devoid of corrupt practices, students industrial work scheme should be redesigned and supervision taken seriously, adequate collaboration between industries and OTM programmes, employment of qualified lecturers and impact assessment should be carried out by owners of public Polytechnics to ascertain the level of growth in the Polytechnics. The finding is supported by Abraham (2019) when he stated that

assuring the quality of educational provision is a fundamental aspect of gaining and maintaining credibility for programmes and that quality assurance is related to accountability, both of which are concerned with maximizing the effectiveness and efficiency of educational system and services in relation to the contexts of their mission as stated. the findings of this study is also in line with the study of Okoli, Utoware and Kaizer (2017) which found that quality assurance strategies should be put in place to promote quality teaching and learning in business education programme for skills acquisition that will enable students contribute to development of society.

The test of the null hypothesis revealed that there were no significant differences in the mean response of experienced and less experience lecturers and also in the mean response of male and female lecturers in the Polytechnics. Thus, the null hypotheses tested were upheld. This implies that neither experienced or less experienced lecturers nor gender had significant effect on the responses of lecturers. This finding corroborates Amesi (2017) who stated that ensuring quality programme that can enhance effective acquisition of skills make the programme to be suitable for the intended purpose and mistakes are eliminated.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that there exist several causes that have hampered the quality of OTM programmes in the Polytechnics. It was also concluded that quality assurance mechanism can be achieved if adopted without compromise.

Recommendations

Arising from the findings and conclusion, the following recommendations are made;

1. Regulatory agencies, such as NBTE that are saddled with accreditation and reaccreditation of Polytechnics /OTM programmes should pay periodic visits to institutions offering OTM programmes to ensure that standards are maintained without compromise.
2. Administrators of OTM programme from top management to school level should make provision for modern technological machines and laboratory equipment to facilitate learning.
3. Qualified lecturers, instructors and technologists should be engaged in the programme to ensure academic excellence. Also programmes for retraining lecturers to upgrade existing knowledge should be organised periodically.
4. The curriculum of OTM programme should be examined if possible periodically to ascertain its relevance. This is important because of the present technological era that has continuously moved on and most times taken those who are not ready unawares.

5. Owners of Polytechnic system should set up impact assessment mechanism to assess the growth or otherwise of the Polytechnic system, with regard to programme suitability in order to correct bad situation before it escalates.
6. The government should provide funds to procure teaching and learning facilities. Such funds can also help in effecting maintenance of available facilities which will help in providing learning adequately.

References

- Anyendu, U. (2020). Entrepreneurial skills, Retrieved 4/03/2020 from decnigeria.com
- Garba, J. H, Jah, R. K. & Dahiru, A (2017) Awareness of quality assurance mechanisms in business education programme in colleges of education in North-East Nigeria for national development. *Association of Business Educators of Nigeria, Conference Proceedings 4 (1) 20-25.*
- Maduewesi, B. U. and Onyechu, J. A. E. (2010) Quality Assurance in Primary Education In Nigeria, Retrieved 12/01/2020 from <http://www.wesoedu.com>
- Nwada, A. O & Seyi, D (2017). Achieving quality assurance in business education for sustainable development. *Association of Business Educators of Nigeria, Conference Proceedings. 4 (1), 26-34.*
- NPE (2014). National Policies on education Lagos; Federal Republic of Nigeria NERDC Press.
- Onyesom, M & Ashibogwu, N.K (2013). Towards Quality Assurance in Business Education in Nigeria; Constraint and Control. *Asian Journal of Business Management, 5 (3) 306-312.*
- Oluwadare, A. A (2019) quality assurance of skill acquisition centuries as perceived by business educators in Ondo State tertiary Institutions. *Association of Business Educators Journal of Nigeria. 6(2), 152-162.*
- Okoli, B. E, Utoware, J. D & Kaizer, A. N (2018) Quality assurance strategies for promoting skill acquisition in business education. *Association of Business Educators of Nigeria Journal. 5(2), 52-62.*
- Sokyes H. P, Wetwan, P. A, Bewaran Y. S (2018) Quality assurance and skill acquisition in Office Technology and Management. *Association of Business Education of Nigeria Journal 5(1), 86-92.*